

First Mexico-UK Interdisciplinary Congress: 200 Years of Academic Excellence

Presentation Title

Water quality communication and public participation in monitoring efforts in Jalisco, Mexico

Abstract

Water resources are facing pressures due to increasing demand and the effects of climate change, making its preservation a priority. Effective management is vital to guarantee access to an adequate supply of good-quality water. In recent years, multiple scientific and technological advancements have been developed to enhance the monitoring of water bodies, providing authorities with sufficient data for informed decision-making. Despite these advances, the growing volume of information has not led to a corresponding improvement in public understanding of water quality, limiting public advocacy for better policies and compliance with existing regulations. Low comprehension can be attributed to multiple deficiencies in the communication process, such as the selection of channels that are not relevant to the public, the use of complex language, and the inexistence of adequate feedback mechanisms. Deficiencies in water quality understanding have also impacted the public participation processes, which are essential for increasing public concern, promoting the search for better solutions, setting policy priorities, and improving the legitimacy of government decisions. In collaboration with researchers from the University of Leeds, specializing in water management and social sciences, we developed a comprehensive survey to examine the public opinions and preferences regarding water quality communications and evaluate the public interest in participating in projects related to monitoring water bodies. The survey was applied to one thousand inhabitants of Jalisco, Mexico, to obtain a statistical representation of the state. We expect that our findings on the public's communication preferences and willingness to engage in monitoring projects will assist public and private institutions in refining their communication strategies and developing tailored projects that foster more effective and inclusive engagement, ultimately contributing to better water management outcomes.

Mini bio

I was born in Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico. I studied biotechnology engineering and a master's in biotechnology at Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico. After completing my master's, I worked as a chemistry professor and then as a water management advisor to the Ministry of Environment and Territorial Development of the state of Jalisco (SEMADET). While working as an advisor, I decided to study for a PhD in Biotechnology focusing on water management. I'm currently completing a research stay at the University of Leeds in the UK. My research interests are automated water quality monitoring, citizen science, and water quality communication.

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Thematic table

Climate Change, Sustainability, and Environmental Policy